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**Regional Influences on Vernacular Architecture of Coastal Region of East Africa
Case Study of 11th to 18th Century Suakin City Buildings**

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Abstract

The history of Suakin architecture and its consequences is not intellectually viable. This study discusses the evolution and subsequent developments of vernacular architecture in the Suakin city with particular reference to its contribution and regional influences on this city. The findings reveal that the architectural features of the historic buildings on Suakin Island have undergone significant changes, transitioning from coral structures to brick buildings. Despite these transformations, the buildings continue to follow a pattern that incorporates circular, semi-circular, and triangular designs, which align with traditional Islamic architectural styles. Another notable feature of these structures is the inclusion of drainage systems, such as rain spouts.

The architectural style of these buildings can be classified within the Hypostyle Hall design category, with some buildings also reflecting the courtyard unit and central courtyard plan. In terms of regional influences, Suakin's architecture is classified as "Arabic Type," while other regional classifications include the "Turkish," "Anglo-Egyptian," and "Red Sea" styles. Additionally, the evolving architectural currents across the coastal regions, such as those seen in the historic buildings of Old Jeddah in Saudi Arabia, Egypt, and Yemen, have similarly shaped Suakin's architectural landscape.

Keywords: Regional Influences, vernacular, Architecture, Coastal Region, East Africa, Case Study, Suakin city, buildings